

Project CHANGES - Spoke 4

D6 – Involvement and Exploitation Strategy – v1.0

30 November 2023

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Authors(s)	Genovese, Gianluca (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1064-2061): Dipartimento di Studi Umanistici, Università Suor Orsola Benincasa Montanari, Roberto, Centro di Ricerca Scienza Nuova, Università Suor Orsola Benincasa Peroni, Silvio (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0530-4305): Dipartimento di Filologia Classica e Italianistica, Università di Bologna
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Spoke information

Scientific coordinator

Silvio Peroni – silvio.peroni@unibo.it – <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0530-4305>

Dipartimento di Filologia Classica e Italianistica

Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna

Via Zamboni 32, 40126 Bologna (BO), Italia

Scientific co-coordinator

Gianluca Genovese – gianluca.genovese@unisob.na.it – <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1064-2061>

Dipartimento di Scienze Umanistiche

Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa

Via Suor Orsola 10, 80135 Napoli (NA), Italia

Spoke partners

No	Name	Acronym	Role
1	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	UNIBO	Spoke leader
2	Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa	UNISOB	Spoke co-leader
3	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CRN	Member
4	DTC Lazio	DTC	Member
5	Engineering	ENG	Member
6	Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro	UNIBA	Member
7	Università degli Studi di Ferrara	UNIFE	Affiliated by "convenzione"
8	Università degli Studi di Firenze	UNIFI	Member
9	Università degli Studi di Parma	UNIPR	Affiliated by "convenzione"
10	Università degli Studi di Torino	UNITO	Member

Executive Summary

The current deliverable is the D9 Involvement and Exploitation Strategy, produced under the WP5 of the Spoke 4.

The deliverable presents the methods and tools identified and prepared by the project to achieve three main goals:

- Identify and involve a number of relevant stakeholders categories in the project activities, according to the quadruple helix engagement approach;
- identify and implement a series of exploitation activities to disseminate the results of the project in scientific communities, through conferences and events;
- design and develop a set of communication tools and materials to reach the targeted audience and maximise the visibility of the project and its outputs.

In order to measure the effectiveness of the defined actions and tools, a list of KPIs and expected results are eventually presented in the document.

Table of content

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION	1
DELIVERABLE HISTORY	2
SPOKE INFORMATION	3
SPOKE PARTNERS	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
TABLE OF CONTENT	5
1. INTRODUCTION	6
2. INVOLVEMENT STRATEGY	8
3. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY	9
4. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY	10
5. EXPECTED RESULTS AND KPIS	18

1. Introduction

This document is the deliverable D9 of the Changes Project that presents the Involvement and Exploitation Strategy set out in relation to three main objectives, corresponding to the three main sections of the document:

- the stakeholders' involvement,
- the exploitation of the project's results and outcomes,
- and the communication with the targeted audiences.

The involvement and exploitation strategy will ensure a coherent set of methods for dissemination and exploitation of scientific results, fostering of knowledge exchange and transfer, co-creation and impact creation.

The strategy presented here responds to the goals of the Spoke 4, which focused on the impact that digital cultural heritage (DCH) and, particularly, of the WP5 on Involvement and Exploitation. This WP aims at maximizing the spoke impact towards the research and cultural heritage communities and society by developing specific communication strategies for supporting the spoke to scale the technologies up at a national level, fostering their adoption in other cultural institutions and developing an ecosystem of services to support citizens and cultural heritage operation by creating cultural offerings as well as new job profiles.

The document includes the activities, objectives, guidelines, and methodologies to disseminate the project results and outcomes as widely as possible among the identified stakeholders and target groups. The deliverable illustrates the set of tools and channels that will be adopted by the project to implement the planned strategy and the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be used to measure the effectiveness of these activities.

The deliverable is articulated to illustrate the overall strategy of the stakeholder involvement and dissemination, broken down by objectives, target groups and key messages. This is

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followed by a description of the tools and channels that the project will adopt to implement the communication and dissemination actions.

This Strategy is also meant to be updated, if necessary, to reflect the progress and directions of the project and to be implemented throughout the entire duration of the project.

The Strategy presented in this document complies with the "LINEE GUIDA PER LE AZIONI DI INFORMAZIONE E COMUNICAZIONE A CURA DEI SOGGETTI ATTUATORI".

2. Involvement Strategy

As stated at the beginning of this document, one of the key objectives of this strategy is to define and implement a set of methods to reach the greatest number of stakeholders, and networks of stakeholders, directly or indirectly involved in the cultural heritage domain (including research and academia, civil society, business, and Public Administrations/ policy makers), according to the quadruple helix engagement approach.

The goals of the involvement efforts are to raise awareness about the project's activities, to give access to the scientific and technical results, as well as to disseminate and ensure uptake of the project's outcomes.

To involve the appropriate stakeholders, the project will carry out the following process:

- identification of the relevant stakeholders' categories;
- identification and definition of different engagement and involvement strategies for the different categories;
- identification and definition of the roles of each stakeholder category in relation to the project's output;
- participation of the identified stakeholders in the project's activities;
- measurement of the levels of engagement and results of their involvement according to the defined KPIs.

The involvement strategy will also aim to build a network of the relevant stakeholders to leverage collaborations and synergies and maximise their impact on the project's outcomes.

The expected results of this activity and the KPIs to measure them are presented in the section 5.

3. Exploitation Strategy

The outputs of the scientific research produced by the project should have appropriate and wide resonance. The project will therefore define coherent methods and tools to maximise the re-use of the scientific outputs and their uptake on a broad scale.

To do this, the project will carry out the following activities:

- Identification of the most relevant results and content to be disseminated and their collection in a shared repository;
- Definition of a structured plan and a shared calendar of scientific publications to be produced by the partners throughout the duration of the project. The template of the shared calendar is provided as a separate annex to this document, and it will be stored for shared use by the Spoke 4 consortium, on the project's repository;
- Preparation of a list of events (conferences, workshops, seminars and lectures) for attendance and participation in order to disseminate the publications and other project's results;
- Identification of scientific journals for the publications (for example Umanistica Digitale);
- Participation and/or organisation of summer schools;
- Organisation of a project's event for the exploitation.

Following the process described above, the team will keep track of both the events and initiatives organised by the consortium in the context of the Spoke 4, and the events and initiatives organised by third parties and attended by the team members.

In terms of dissemination of the Spoke 4 results, all the deliverables will be published in Open Access and uploaded by the Spoke leader to Zenodo¹ (a generalist data repository

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/>

funded by the EU which guarantees long term preservation, which attributes DOIs to all archived datasets and all versions, supports open licenses and different access levels) using a CC-BY license.

The expected results of this activity and the KPIs to measure them are presented in the section 5.

4. Communication Strategy

The communication activities have a crucial role to ensure the visibility and reach of the project towards the targeted communities. These activities are also complementary to the Stakeholders Involvement and Exploitation, contributing to the achievement of their specific results. Therefore, the communication tasks require a careful selection of the channels and methodologies to be adopted.

The communication strategy includes:

- the definition and development of a distinctive and impactful brand identity;
- the identification, design and development of digital (and non-digital) tools and platforms to reach the identified audiences and amplify the project's impact;
- the selection of key messages, based on the characteristics of the identified target groups.

The **Brand identity** allows to maintain stylistic coherence between the material used to disseminate the results and the content to be disseminated. The CHANGES project has already developed a coherent brand identity, composed by the materials presented below. The project logo, shown here below, available with different backgrounds (black and white) and colour fonts:

Figura 1 CHANGES Logo with black background

Concerning the logo, it has been agreed that, for the following purposes, the consortium is allowed to use it without the need to specific permission by the Foundation:

1. participation in conferences and related communications in proceedings and programs;
2. participation in seminars, workshops, lectures, and related communications in proceedings and programs;
3. participation/organisation of summer schools and related communications in proceedings and programs;
4. publication on journals;
5. organisations of seminars/ hackathons, scientific or dissemination tutorials on the topics (both theoretical/cultural and technological) related to the Spoke 4.

The banner including the project logo and the institutional PNRR logos, shown here below, available with different backgrounds (black and white) and colour fonts:

Figura 2 PNRR Banner with CHANGES Logo

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The PowerPoint template to be used for the project's presentations, as shown below:

Figura 3 Cover Slide of the Powerpoint Template

The project's letterhead, as shown below:

Titolo

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet consectetur adipiscing elit. Nam mi ante, luctus sed ipsum non, dapibus viverra quam. Fusce quis conque eros. Aenean vitae elit porttitor, placerat neque mollis, efficitur tellis. Vestibulum ante ipsum primis in faucibus, orci luctus et ultrices posuere cubilia curae; Maecenas purus orci, vulputate sed mi ac pharetra vehicula enim. Nullam efficitur interdum rhoncus. Praesent condimentum, ex eu cursus varius, nisi enim ullamcorper risus, vehicula euismod odio nibh at turpis. Etiam eleifend lectus nisi. Suscipiendae sit amet cursus sapien. Proin varius dictum elit vitae consectetur. Vivamus mauris sem, suscipit ac conque, at fermentum at diam. Donec at maximus tellus. Aenean a augue, non purus conivallis porttitor bibendum in massa. In accumsan quam, nisi sit amet fringilla quam euismod in. Duis mauris eros, accumsan sed lectus vitae, volutpat dignissim purus. Integer hendrerit, mi id sollicitudin, elitum purus orci faucibus massa, vitae pharetra neque turpis sit amet quam.

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Figura 4 CHANGES Letterhead

- the template for the project's deliverables, as shown below;

Project CHANGES - Spoke 4

D<deliverable number> – <deliverable title> – v<version number>
<date of publication>

Deliverable information

Work package	WP<WP number>
Deliverable leader	<acronym> Institution deliverable leader
Author(s)	<family names> <given names> [<ORCID URL>]; <full affiliation> <family names> <given names> [<ORCID URL>]; <full affiliation> ...
Deliverable status	<choose: Draft, Final>
Deliverable version	v<version number – 0.x for drafts, 1.x for final versions>
Date	<day> <month, in English> <year>

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Figura 5 CHANGES Deliverable Template (Cover Page)

The second element of the communication strategy is the **project's website**, which provisionally is available at this [link](#), but will be shortly restructured and will include also analytics to monitor traffic and actions by users. The website presents the following sections:

- Chi siamo (about the Foundation, the partners news and events)
- I partners
- Spokes (a presentation of the 9 spokes)
- Lavora con noi (where available job positions are published)
- Fondazione Trasparente (reporting the administrative information about the Foundation)
- Contacts

Figura 6 Homepage of the CHANGES website

The third element of the communication strategy is represented by the **social media** channels. The presence on social media is essential for of any communication and dissemination strategy, as it enables direct contact with the audience and facilitates the stakeholders' engagement. The digital channels (website and social media) are meant to be both a tool for dissemination, but also a point of contact between the project (spokes), the hub, and the external audience.

Currently, CHANGES has launched the LinkedIn page, available at this [link](#). Other social media platforms (like YouTube and Instagram are under preparation).

Figura 7 Screenshot of the CHANGES' LinkedIn Page

Finally, the communication activities also include a periodical **newsletter**. At the moment, the first release of the newsletter was published.

Figure 1 Screenshot of the CHANGES Newsletter

The form features the CHANGES logo at the top, followed by the sub-header 'CULTURAL HERITAGE ACTIVE INNOVATION FOR NEX-GEN SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY EXTENDED PARTNERSHIP'. The main heading is 'NEWSLETTER Fondazione CHANGES'. Below this is a section for uploading files, with a 'Cambia account' link and a cloud icon. A paragraph explains that the user's name and photo from their Google account will be registered upon file upload. A final note states that all uploaded files will be shared with the organization. A red asterisk indicates a mandatory question.

Figure 8 Google Form to sign up to CHANGES newsletter

To publish content in the newsletter, it is agreed to preliminary inform either the spoke leader and the dissemination leader, i.e., UNIBO and UNISOB.

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5. Expected Results and KPIs

In relation to the Involvement and Exploitation Strategy, two specific expected results were already identified in the project proposal. They are as follows:

- R9: Development of exploitation strategies for maximizing reusability and enabling to scale up narratives and prototypes at the national level – M36;
- R10: Creation of a workflow to improve the cultural value of cultural heritage objects through approaches for digital dissemination (e.g., focused on the society, high school programs and museum networks) and how they affect the potential audiences – M36.

The KPI to evaluate the results will be:

- For R9 Qualitative response of the community involved (QLC), and Quantitative size of the community involved (QNC);
- For R10, the KPI will be QLC.

To measure the effectiveness and impact of the Involvement, Exploitation, and Communication activities carried out, a set of additional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) has been identified:

- For stakeholders involvement:
 - o the identification of at least 10-15 stakeholders to be involved in the Spoke 4
 - o the identification of at least 1 professional network
- for exploitation:
 - o the preparation of at least 6 publications / per spoke (note that the following should be included for acknowledgements of scientific publications: *Progetto*

*PE 0000020 CHANGES, - CUP [...], PNRR Missione 4 Componente 2 Investimento 1.3, finanziato dall'Unione europea – NextGenerationEU". (ITA)
/ Project PE 0000020 CHANGES - CUP [...], NRP Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.3, Funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU". (ENG)*

- the participation in at least 3 conferences/events for scientific dissemination in three years;
- for communication:
 - the publication of 1 posts on social media / per month
 - the publication of 1 article for the newsletter / every two issues.